

Corrigendum

Corrigendum to “*Cyperus surinamensis* Rottb. (Cyperaceae): A New Record for the Flora of Odisha, India”

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In the article entitled “***Cyperus surinamensis* Rottb. (Cyperaceae): A New Record for the Flora of Odisha, India**” (Devi et al., 2025), the species was reported as a new record for the flora of Odisha. However, an earlier short communication by Jena et al. (2024), documenting the occurrence of this species from the Eastern Ghats of India, including Odisha, was inadvertently overlooked. Accordingly, the record reported in our paper should be regarded as a “**Further distributional record of *Cyperus surinamensis* Rottb. (Cyperaceae) from Odisha, India**”. This correction does not affect the taxonomic identity or other findings presented in the original publication.

References

- Devi RS, Marndi S, Mishra S, Rout S and Kumar S. (2025). *Cyperus surinamensis* Rottb. (Cyperaceae): A New Record for the Flora of Odisha, India. Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation. 9(4): 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17448261>
- Jena NK, Tudu S, Priyadarshini S and Sahu SC. (2024). *Cyperus surinamensis* Rottb. (Cyperaceae): A new record for Eastern Ghats, India. Nelumbo. 66(1): 130–131. <https://doi.org/10.20324/nelumbo/v66/2024/173069>